

Local Property of a Factored Fourier Series using Absolute Norlund Indexed Summability

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Abstract

In this paper we have established a theorem on the local property of absolute Norlund indexed-summability of Factored Fourier series.

Keywords: $|N, p_n|_k$ - summability; $|N, p_n, \alpha_n|_k$ - summability; $|\overline{N}, p_n; \alpha_n, \delta|_k$ - summability and Fourier series.

1. Introduction

Let $\sum a_n$ be a given infinite series with sequence of partial sums $\{s_n\}$. Let $\{p_n\}$ be a sequence of positive real constants such that

$$(1.1) \quad P_n = \sum_{\nu=0}^n p_\nu \rightarrow \infty \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty \quad (P_{-i} = p_{-i} = 0, i \geq 1)$$

The sequence-to-sequence transformation

$$(1.2) \quad t_n = \frac{1}{P_n} \sum_{\nu=0}^n p_{n-\nu} s_\nu$$

defines (N, p_n) -mean of the sequence $\{s_n\}$ generated by the sequence of coefficients $\{p_n\}$. The series

$\sum a_n$ is said to be summable $|N, p_n|_k$, $k \geq 1$, if

$$(1.3) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n} \right)^{k-1} |t_n - t_{n-1}|^k < \infty.$$

For $k = 1$, $|N, p_n|_k$ - summability is same as $|N, p_n|$ - summability.

When $p_n = 1$, for all n and $k = 1$, $|N, p_n|_k$ - summability is same as $|C, 1|$ summability.

Let $\{\alpha_n\}$ be any sequence of positive numbers. The series $\sum a_n$ is said to be summable $|N, p_n, \alpha_n|_k$, $k \geq 1$, if

$$(1.4) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha_n^{k-1} |t_n - t_{n-1}|^k < \infty,$$

Where $\{t_n\}$ is as defined in (5.1.2). The series $\sum a_n$ is said to be summable $|N, p_n, \alpha_n; \delta|_k$, $k \geq 1, \delta \geq 0$, if

$$(1.5) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha_n^{\delta k + k - 1} |t_n - t_{n-1}|^k < \infty.$$

For $\delta = 0$, the summability method $|N, p_n, \alpha_n; \delta|_k$, $k \geq 1, \delta \geq 0$, reduces to the summability method $|N, p_n, \alpha_n|_k$, $k \geq 1$.

For any real number γ , the series $\sum a_n$ is said to be summable by the summability method $|N, p_n, \alpha_n; \delta, \gamma|_k$, $k \geq 1, \delta \geq 0$, if

$$(1.6) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k + k - 1)} |t_n - t_{n-1}|^k < \infty.$$

For $\gamma = 1$, the summability method $|N, p_n, \alpha_n; \delta, \gamma|_k$, $k \geq 1, \delta \geq 0$, any real γ , reduces to the method $|N, p_n, \alpha_n; \delta|_k$, $k \geq 1, \delta \geq 0$.

A sequence $\{\lambda_n\}$ is said to be convex if $\Delta^2 \lambda_n \geq 0$ for every positive integer n .

Let $f(t)$ be a periodic function with period 2π and integrable in the sense of Lebesgue over $(-\pi, \pi)$. Without loss of generality we may assume that the constant term in the Fourier series of $f(t)$ is zero, so that

$$(1.7) \quad f(t) \sim \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \cos nt + b_n \sin nt) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n(t)$$

It is well known that the convergence of Fourier series at $t = x$ is a local property of $f(t)$ (i.e., it depends only on the behavior of $f(t)$ in an arbitrarily small neighborhood of x) and hence the summability of the Fourier series at $t = x$ by any regular linear method is also a local property of $f(t)$.

2. Known theorems

Dealing with the $|\overline{N}, p_n|_k$ - summability of an infinite series Bor [1] proved the following theorem:

Theorem-2.1

Let $k \geq 1$ and let the sequences $\{p_n\}$ and $\{\lambda_n\}$ be such that

$$(2.1.1) \quad \Delta X_n = O\left(\frac{1}{n}\right),$$

$$(2.1.2) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n^{k-1} \frac{|\lambda_n|^k + |\lambda_{n+1}|^k}{n} < \infty,$$

and

$$(2.1.3) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (X_n^k + 1) |\Delta \lambda_n| < \infty,$$

where $X_n = \frac{P_n}{np_n}$. Then the summability $|\overline{N}, p_n|_k$ of the factored Fourier series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n(t) \lambda_n X_n$ at a point can be ensured by the local property.

Subsequently, Misra et. al. [2] proved the following theorem on the local property of $|N, p_n, \alpha_n|_k$ summability of factored Fourier series:

Theorem-2.2

Let $k \geq 1$. Suppose $\{\lambda_n\}$ be a convex sequence such that $\sum n^{-1} \lambda_n$ is convergent and $\{p_n\}$ be a sequence such that

$$(2.2.1) \quad \Delta X_n = O\left(\frac{1}{n}\right),$$

$$(2.2.2) \quad \frac{P_{n-r-1}}{P_n} = O\left(\frac{P_{n-r-1}}{P_{n-1}} \frac{P_r}{p_r}\right),$$

$$(2.2.3) \quad \sum_{n=r+1}^{m+1} (\alpha_n)^{k-1} \frac{P_{n-r}}{P_n} = O\left(\frac{p_r}{P_r}\right),$$

$$(2.2.4) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n^{k-1} \frac{|\lambda_n|^k}{n} < \infty,$$

and

$$(2.2.5) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n^{k-1} \frac{|\Delta \lambda_n|^k}{n} < \infty,$$

Where $X_n = \frac{P_n}{np_n}$. Then the summability $|N, p_n, \alpha_n|_k$, $k \geq 1$ of the factored Fourier series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n(t) \lambda_n X_n$ at a point can be ensured by the local property, where $\{\alpha_n\}$ is a sequence of positive numbers.

Recently, Paikray et al. [3] proved the following theorem on the local property of $|N, p_n, \alpha_n, \delta|_k$ summability of factored Fourier series:

Theorem-2.3

Let $k \geq 1$. Suppose $\{\lambda_n\}$ be a convex sequence such that $\sum n^{-1}\lambda_n$ is convergent and $\{p_n\}$ be a sequence such that

$$(2.3.1) \quad \Delta X_n = O\left(\frac{1}{n}\right),$$

$$(2.3.2) \quad \frac{P_{n-r-1}}{P_n} = O\left(\frac{P_{n-r-1}}{P_{n-1}} \frac{P_r}{p_r}\right),$$

$$(2.3.3) \quad \sum_{n=r+1}^{m+1} (\alpha_n)^{\delta k+k-1} \frac{P_{n-r}}{P_n} = O\left(\frac{P_r}{P_r}\right),$$

$$(2.3.4) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n^{k-1} \frac{|\lambda_n|^k}{n} < \infty,$$

and

$$(2.3.5) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n^{k-1} \frac{|\Delta \lambda_n|^k}{n} < \infty,$$

where $X_n = \frac{P_n}{np_n}$. Then the summability $|N, p_n, \alpha_n, \delta|_k$, $k \geq 1$ of the factored Fourier series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n(t) \lambda_n X_n$ at a point can be ensured by the local property, where $\{\alpha_n\}$ is a sequence of positive numbers.

In the present paper we have established the following theorem on $|N, p_n, \alpha_n, \delta, \gamma|_k$ - summability of a factored Fourier series through its local property.

3. Main theorem

Let $k \geq 1$. Suppose $\{\lambda_n\}$ be a convex sequence such that $\sum n^{-1}\lambda_n$ is convergent and $\{p_n\}$ be a sequence such that

$$(3.1) \quad \Delta X_n = O\left(\frac{1}{n}\right),$$

$$(3.2) \quad \frac{P_{n-r-1}}{P_n} = O\left(\frac{P_{n-r-1}}{P_{n-1}} \frac{P_r}{p_r}\right)$$

$$(3.3) \quad \sum_{n=r+1}^{m+1} (\alpha_n)^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \frac{P_{n-r}}{P_n} = O\left(\frac{P_r}{P_r}\right),$$

$$(3.4) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n^{k-1} \frac{|\lambda_n|^k}{n} < \infty,$$

and

$$(3.5) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n^{k-1} \frac{|\Delta \lambda_n|^k}{n} < \infty,$$

where $X_n = \frac{P_n}{np_n}$. Then the summability $|N, p_n, \alpha_n, \delta, \gamma|_k, k \geq 1$ of the factored Fourier series

$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n(t) \lambda_n X_n$ at a point can be ensured by the local property, where $\{\alpha_n\}$ is a sequence of positive numbers.

4. Required lemma

In order to prove the above theorem we require the following lemma:

Lemma

Let $k \geq 1$ and suppose $\{\lambda_n\}$ be a convex sequence such that $\sum n^{-1} \lambda_n$ is convergent and $\{p_n\}$ be a sequence such that the conditions (3.1)-(3.5) are satisfied. If $\{s_n\}$ is bounded, then for the sequence of positive numbers $\{\alpha_n\}$ the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \lambda_n X_n$ is summable $|N, p_n, \alpha_n, \delta|_k^\gamma, k \geq 1, \delta \geq 0$.

Proof of the lemma

Let $\{T_n\}$ denote the (N, p_n) -mean of the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \lambda_n X_n$. Then by definition we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_n &= \frac{1}{P_n} \sum_{v=0}^n p_{n-v} \sum_{r=0}^v a_r \lambda_r X_r \\ &= \frac{1}{P_n} \sum_{r=0}^n a_r \lambda_r X_r \sum_{v=r}^n p_{n-v} \\ &= \frac{1}{P_n} \sum_{r=0}^n a_r P_{n-r} \lambda_r X_r \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} T_n - T_{n-1} &= \frac{1}{P_n} \sum_{r=1}^n P_{n-r} a_r \lambda_r X_r - \frac{1}{P_{n-1}} \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} P_{n-r-1} a_r \lambda_r X_r \\ &= \sum_{r=1}^n \left(\frac{P_{n-r}}{P_n} - \frac{P_{n-r-1}}{P_{n-1}} \right) a_r \lambda_r X_r \\ &= \frac{1}{P_n P_{n-1}} \sum_{r=1}^n (P_{n-r} P_{n-1} - P_{n-r-1} P_n) a_r \lambda_r X_r \\ &= \frac{1}{P_n P_{n-1}} \left[\sum_{r=1}^{n-1} \Delta \{ (P_{n-r} P_{n-1} - P_{n-r-1} P_n) \lambda_r X_r \} \right] \sum_{v=1}^r a_v \\ &= \frac{1}{P_n P_{n-1}} \left[\sum_{r=1}^{n-1} (P_{n-r} P_{n-1} - P_{n-r-1} P_n) \lambda_r X_r s_r \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} (P_{n-r-1} P_{n-1} - P_{n-r-2} P_n) \Delta \lambda_r X_r s_r \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} (P_{n-r-1} P_{n-1} - P_{n-r-2} P_n) \lambda_{r+1} \Delta X_r s_r \right] \end{aligned}$$

(by Abel's transformation)

$$= T_{n,1} + T_{n,2} + T_{n,3} + T_{n,4} + T_{n,5} + T_{n,6}, \text{ (say).}$$

In order to complete the proof of the theorem by using Minokowski's inequality, it is sufficient to show that

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} |T_{n,i}|^k < \infty \text{ for } i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6.$$

Now, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} |T_{n,1}|^k &= \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left| \frac{1}{P_n P_{n-1}} \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} p_{n-r} P_{n-1} \lambda_r X_r s_r \right|^k \\ &\leq \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \frac{1}{P_n} \left(\sum_{r=1}^{n-1} p_{n-r} |\lambda_r|^k |s_r|^k X_r^k \right) \left(\frac{1}{P_n} \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} p_{n-r} \right)^{k-1} \\ &= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m |\lambda_r|^k X_r^k \sum_{n=r+1}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left(\frac{p_{n-r}}{P_n} \right) \\ &= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m |\lambda_r|^k X_r^k \frac{P_r}{P_r}, \text{ by (3.3)} \\ &= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m |\lambda_r|^k X_r^{k-1} \frac{P_r}{P_r} \frac{P_r}{r p_r}, \text{ as } X_n = \frac{P_n}{n p_n} \\ &= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m X_r^{k-1} \frac{|\lambda_r|^k}{r} \\ &= O(1) \text{ as } m \rightarrow \infty, \text{ by (5.3.4).} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Next, } \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} |T_{n,2}|^k &= \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left| \frac{1}{P_n P_{n-1}} \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} p_{n-r-1} P_n \lambda_r X_r s_r \right|^k \\ &\leq \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \frac{1}{P_{n-1}} \left(\sum_{r=1}^{n-1} p_{n-r-1} |\lambda_r|^k |s_r|^k X_r^k \right) \left(\frac{1}{P_{n-1}} \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} p_{n-r-1} \right)^{k-1} \\ &= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m |\lambda_r|^k X_r^k \sum_{n=r+1}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left(\frac{p_{n-r-1}}{P_{n-1}} \right) \\ &= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m |\lambda_r|^k X_r^k \frac{P_r}{P_r}, \text{ by (5.3.3)} \\ &= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m |\lambda_r|^k X_r^{k-1} \frac{P_r}{P_r} \frac{P_r}{r p_r}, \text{ as } X_n = \frac{P_n}{n p_n} \end{aligned}$$

$$= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m X_r^{k-1} \frac{|\lambda_r|^k}{r}$$

$$= O(1) \text{ as } m \rightarrow \infty, \text{ by (3.4).}$$

Further,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} |T_{n,3}|^k &= \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left| \frac{1}{P_n P_{n-1}} \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} P_{n-r-1} P_{n-1} \Delta \lambda_r X_r s_r \right|^k \\ &\leq \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \frac{1}{P_n} \left(\sum_{r=1}^{n-1} P_{n-r-1} |\Delta \lambda_r|^k |s_r|^k X_r^k \right) \left(\frac{1}{P_n} \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} P_{n-r-1} |\Delta \lambda_r| \right)^{k-1} \\ &= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m |\Delta \lambda_r|^k X_r^k \sum_{n=r+1}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left(\frac{P_{n-r-1}}{P_n} \right) \\ &\quad \left(\text{Since } \frac{1}{P_n} \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} P_{n-r-1} |\Delta \lambda_r| \leq \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} |\Delta \lambda_r| = O(1) \right) \\ &= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m |\Delta \lambda_r|^k X_r^k \frac{P_r}{P_r}, \text{ by (3.3)} \\ &= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m |\Delta \lambda_r|^k X_r^{k-1} \frac{P_r}{P_r} \frac{P_r}{r P_r}, \text{ as } X_n = \frac{P_n}{n P_n} \\ &= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m X_r^{k-1} \frac{|\Delta \lambda_r|^k}{r} \\ &= O(1) \text{ as } m \rightarrow \infty, \text{ by (3.5).} \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} |T_{n,4}|^k &= \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left| \frac{1}{P_n P_{n-1}} \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} P_{n-r-2} P_n \Delta \lambda_r X_r s_r \right|^k \\ &\leq \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \frac{1}{P_{n-1}} \left(\sum_{r=1}^{n-1} P_{n-r-2} |\Delta \lambda_r|^k |s_r|^k X_r^k \right) \left(\frac{1}{P_{n-1}} \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} P_{n-r-2} |\Delta \lambda_r| \right)^{k-1} \\ &= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m |\Delta \lambda_r|^k X_r^k \sum_{n=r+1}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left(\frac{P_{n-r-2}}{P_{n-1}} \right) \text{ (as above)} \\ &= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m |\Delta \lambda_r|^k X_r^k \frac{P_r}{P_r}, \text{ by (5.3.3)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m |\Delta \lambda_r|^k X_r^{k-1} \frac{P_r}{P_r} \frac{P_r}{r P_r}, \text{ as } X_n = \frac{P_n}{n p_n} \\
&= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m X_r^{k-1} \frac{|\Delta \lambda_r|^k}{r} \\
&= O(1) \text{ as } m \rightarrow \infty, \text{ by (3.5).}
\end{aligned}$$

Again

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} |T_{n,5}|^k &= \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left| \frac{1}{P_n P_{n-1}} \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} P_{n-r-1} P_{n-1} \lambda_{r+1} \Delta X_r S_r \right|^k \\
&= \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left| \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} \frac{P_{n-r-1}}{P_n} \lambda_{r+1} \Delta X_r S_r \right|^k \\
&= \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left| \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} \frac{P_{n-r-1}}{P_{n-1}} \frac{P_r}{P_r} \lambda_{r+1} \Delta X_r S_r \right|^k \text{ by (3.2)} \\
&= \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left| \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} \frac{P_{n-r-1}}{P_{n-1}} \frac{P_r}{P_r} \lambda_{r+1} S_r \frac{1}{r} \right|^k \text{ by (3.1)} \\
&= \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left| \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} \frac{P_{n-r-1}}{P_{n-1}} \frac{P_r}{P_r} \lambda_{r+1} S_r X_r \frac{P_r}{P_r} \right|^k, \text{ as } X_n = \frac{P_n}{n p_n} \\
&= \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left\{ \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} \frac{P_{n-r-1}}{P_{n-1}} |\lambda_{r+1}|^k |S_r|^k X_r^k \right\} \left\{ \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} \frac{P_{n-r-1}}{P_{n-1}} \right\}^{k-1} \\
&= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m |\lambda_{r+1}|^k X_r^k \sum_{n=r+1}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left(\frac{P_{n-r-1}}{P_{n-1}} \right) \\
&= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m |\lambda_{r+1}|^k X_r^{k-1} \frac{P_r}{P_r} \frac{P_r}{r P_r}, \text{ as } X_n = \frac{P_n}{n p_n} \text{ and by (3.3)} \\
&= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m \frac{|\lambda_{r+1}|^k}{r} X_r^{k-1}, \\
&= O(1) \text{ as } m \rightarrow \infty, \text{ by (3.4).}
\end{aligned}$$

Finally,

$$\sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} |T_{n,6}|^k = \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left| \frac{1}{P_n P_{n-1}} \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} P_{n-r-2} P_n \lambda_{r+1} \Delta X_r S_r \right|^k$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left| \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} \frac{P_{n-r-2}}{P_{n-1}} \lambda_{r+1} \Delta X_r s_r \right|^k \\
&= \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left| \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} \frac{P_{n-r-2}}{P_{n-2}} \frac{P_r}{P_r} \lambda_{r+1} \Delta X_r s_r \right|^k, \text{ by (3.2)} \\
&= \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left| \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} \frac{P_{n-r-2}}{P_{n-2}} \frac{P_r}{P_r} \lambda_{r+1} s_r \frac{1}{r} \right|^k, \text{ by (3.1)} \\
&= \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left| \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} \frac{P_{n-r-2}}{P_{n-2}} \frac{P_r}{P_r} \lambda_{r+1} s_r X_r \frac{P_r}{P_r} \right|^k, \text{ as } X_n = \frac{P_n}{np_n} \\
&= \sum_{n=2}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left\{ \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} \frac{P_{n-r-2}}{P_{n-2}} |\lambda_{r+1}|^k |s_r|^k X_r^k \right\} \left\{ \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} \frac{P_{n-r-2}}{P_{n-2}} \right\}^{k-1} \\
&= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m |\lambda_{r+1}|^k X_r^k \sum_{n=r+1}^{m+1} \alpha_n^{\gamma(\delta k+k-1)} \left(\frac{P_{n-r-2}}{P_{n-2}} \right) \\
&= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m |\lambda_{r+1}|^k X_r^{k-1} \frac{P_r}{P_r} \frac{P_r}{rp_r}, \text{ as } X_n = \frac{P_n}{np_n} \text{ and by(3.3)} \\
&= O(1) \sum_{r=1}^m \frac{|\lambda_{r+1}|^k}{r} X_r^{k-1}, \\
&= O(1) \text{ as } m \rightarrow \infty, \text{ by (3.4).}
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of the Lemma.

5. Proof of the theorem

Since the behavior of the Fourier series, as far as convergence is concerned, for a particular value of x depends on the behavior of the function in the immediate neighborhood of this point only, the truth of the theorem is necessarily the consequence of the Lemma.

6. Conclusion

Putting $\delta = 0$ and $\alpha = \frac{P_n}{P_n}$ with $\delta=0$, the result of Misra et al. [2] and the result of H.Bor [1] can be achieved

respectively from the result established in the present chapter under a few varying condition. Further there is a reach scope to work in this area for different indexed summability methods with additional parameter.

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